

The Ethics of Teaching Across the Faith-Science Boundary

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This is a short case that aims to help teachers and students reflect on the ethics of teaching across disciplinary boundaries, specifically in the area of the faith-science discussion in evolutionary biology. The case presents the question whether it is ethical for a biology professor to use his authority to make statements on a domain that is not his own.

Keywords: education, science- religion, foreign gaze, abuse of authority

During a class on evolutionary biology, the lecturer, who is a full professor in biology, briefly mentions the young-earth creationist stance that the earth, and the species on it, were created as-is approximately four thousand years ago. After pointing out that this stance contradicts the scientific understanding of the process of evolution, he remarks that this is just another example of the irrationality of religious belief.

When the time comes for questions at the end of the lecture, one student asks whether the remark about the irrationality of religious belief is not too sweeping a statement, given that not all religious people, not even all Christians, subscribe to young-earth creationism; that even young-earth creationists try to find rational arguments for their beliefs; and finally that the very institution of the university has historically arisen in a religious, specifically Christian context. Even though one might disagree with their views, the student argues, it is difficult to accuse all religion or all of Christianity of irrationality.

The professor responds by saying that there is no scientific evidence for the existence of a God and asks the student whether she knows of any such evidence. When the student wants to elaborate on why this might not be the right question to ask, the professor insists on having his question answered. When the student cannot produce the requested scientific evidence, he concludes that religious belief in a God is irrational at its core, because it believes in something without sufficient evidence.

Questions for teachers and students

1. Is the biology professor providing an insider or outsider perspective on religious, specifically Christian, beliefs? Is his a “foreign gaze” on religiosity?
2. Do you think that the way the professor treats the student is problematic? If so, why?
3. Do you think that by pronouncing himself on religious beliefs from his authority as a biology professor, the professor is utilizing his authority correctly, or is this an abuse of authority?